

AUTOMATED DASHBOARDS FOR AWS SERVICES MONITORING AND PLACEMENT DATA

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Abstract: Cloud computing has become an integral part of modern business operations, offering flexibility, scalability, and cost-efficiency. However, the migration to the cloud brings forth a new set of challenges, with security being a top concern. Organizations need to continuously monitor and audit their cloud environments to identify vulnerabilities, detect threats, and ensure compliance with security standards. In today's digital landscape, cloud computing has become essential for organizations, offering scalability and cost-effectiveness. However, security remains a top concern. Traditional monitoring processes lack agility and real-time insights. To address this, our project leverages Cloud Computing and Machine Learning to revolutionize cloud security management. It offers real-time monitoring of AWS infrastructure with proactive anomaly detection and alarms. Expanding its capabilities, our platform also provides comprehensive monitoring of content within AWS environments. Specifically, we provide a comprehensive dashboard for monitoring student placement dataset uploaded to AWS. This expanded functionality enhances the platform's utility by offering insights into both the performance and security of cloud services, as well as the data they host. This enhancement empowers educational institutions and recruitment agencies to gain insights into candidate performance. Leveraging the details available, placement related personnel can try to anticipate future placement outcomes and optimize recruitment strategies, ultimately driving greater efficiency and success.

Keywords: Cloud Computing, Auditing, Cloud Security, User-friendly Dashboard, AWS(Amazon Web Services), S3(Simple Storage Service), Amazon CloudWatch, ML(Machine Learning), Python, Microsoft Power BI, Anomaly, Data Analytics, Student Placement, Recruitment and Real-time Monitoring.

I. INTRODUCTION

The "Automated Dashboard for AWS Services Monitoring and Placement Data" project ambitiously merges cloud security auditing and student placement data visualization, leveraging Cloud Computing and Machine Learning (ML) to innovate in both realms. The primary objective targets revolutionizing cloud security auditing by automating the process, collecting data from cloud service providers, subjecting it to ML analysis to detect anomalies, and presenting findings through user-friendly dashboards and reports. Real-time alerts and compliance monitoring ensure proactive responses to security incidents and adherence to regulations. Simultaneously, a secondary objective involves visualizing students' placement data stored in the cloud, empowering educational institutions with insights into placement trends like employment rates, industry sectors, and geographic distribution. By integrating real-time updates and customizable filters, this dashboard aids institutions in strategic decision-making to enhance student success and institutional advancement while reinforcing cloud security and reducing operational overhead.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

A. *Intelligent Role-Based Access Control Model and Framework Using Semantic Business Roles in Multi-Domain Environments*

This paper [1] presents an access control framework that employs semantic business roles and intelligent agents within an Intelligent RBAC (I-RBAC) model. Real-world occupational entitlements are incorporated, and ontology creation is automated through intelligent agents. The effectiveness of the model is demonstrated through implementation results in dynamic multi-domain environments.

B. *An Efficient Data Auditing Protocol With a Novel Sampling Verification Algorithm*

The paper [5] discusses challenges encountered by existing data auditing schemes, particularly those adhering to Ateniese et al.'s framework, such as repeated sampling causing detection delays and risking data loss. In response, this paper introduces an optimized sampling verification algorithm designed to enhance data integrity in cloud environments. The proposed scheme is noted for its security, swift identification of corrupted blocks, and dynamic auditing capabilities.

C. *Privacy-Preserving Cloud Auditing for Multiple Users Scheme with Authorization and Traceability*

The paper [2] presents a novel privacy-preserving cloud auditing scheme designed for multiple users, incorporating certificate-less signature technology. It assures user identity anonymity, enables collaborative traceability by managers, and effectively combats denial-of-service attacks. Noteworthy features include support for user revocation, ensuring security without the intricacies of certificate management. Comprehensive analyses attest to its proven security and efficiency.

D. *A Survey on Securing Federated Learning Analysis of Applications, Attacks, Challenges, and Trends*

This paper [3] explores Federated Learning (FL) as a privacy-preserving paradigm for training machine learning models. It scrutinizes the vulnerabilities that impact user privacy and model performance, offering mitigation strategies to address these challenges. Through an analysis of FL applications, the paper emphasizes the pivotal role of security strategies in upholding user privacy and optimizing model performance within FL frameworks.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Upload Student Placement Data to S3 Bucket:

This initial step involves transferring the student placement data, which could include information such as student profiles, internship details, and employment records, to an Amazon Simple Storage Service (S3) bucket [8]. By storing this data in an S3 bucket, it becomes accessible for subsequent processing and analysis.

B. Enable Access Logging on S3 Bucket:

Access logging is activated on the S3 bucket where the student placement data is stored. This logging functionality records every interaction or request made to the bucket, including details like the identity of the requester, the time of the request, and the specific actions performed. Enabling access logging provides a comprehensive audit trail of bucket activity, which is essential for monitoring and security purposes.

C. Query Access Logs with Amazon Athena:

Amazon Athena, a serverless query service, is utilized to query the access logs stored in the S3 bucket [7]. SQL queries are crafted to extract specific information from the access logs, such as patterns of access, frequency of requests, or details about specific interactions with the data. This allows for deeper analysis of how the placement data is being accessed and utilized.

D. Perform Anomaly Detection with Lambda and CloudWatch:

Anomaly detection is conducted using AWS Lambda functions in conjunction with Amazon CloudWatch. Lambda functions are event-driven, serverless compute services that can be triggered in response to specific events, such as changes in access patterns detected in the S3 access logs. CloudWatch provides monitoring and management for AWS resources, allowing Lambda functions to be triggered based on predefined metrics or alarms. By leveraging these services, anomalies in access patterns, such as unusually high request rates or unauthorized access attempts, can be detected in real-time.

E. Trigger Email Notifications for Anomalies:

Upon detecting anomalies in the access patterns of the student placement data, a Lambda function is triggered to send email notifications to designated recipients. These email notifications serve as alerts, notifying stakeholders, such as system administrators or security personnel, about the detected anomalies. The notifications typically include details about the nature of the anomaly, the affected data, and recommendations for further investigation or action. This prompt notification mechanism enables swift response to potential security threats or irregularities in data access.

F. Visualize Placement Data and Access Data in Power BI:

The placement data is visualized in Power BI [9],[10], empowering educational institutions and recruitment agencies with actionable insights into candidate performance. These insights enable stakeholders to anticipate future placement outcomes and optimize recruitment strategies for enhanced efficiency and success. Additionally, access data is visualized in Power BI through interactive dashboards and reports, providing comprehensive insights derived from meticulous analysis.

Fig 1: Methodology Diagram

IV. RESULTS

Fig 2: Login page

Fig 3: Home Page

Fig 4: AWS Service Dashboard

Fig 5: Page 1 of student placement dashboard

Fig 6: Page 2 of student placement dashboard

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In conclusion, the implementation of automated reporting and dashboards for cloud security audits utilizing ML technologies has significantly improved the efficiency and effectiveness of monitoring and analyzing S3 access data. By automating processes that were previously manual and time-consuming, the project has addressed critical challenges such as the lack of real-time insights and the risk of human errors in monitoring cloud resources. Also by providing another crucial dashboard for identifying potential students for placement opportunities will be beneficial for the placement department of any related educational institute. The integration of anomaly detection mechanisms and email notifications further enhances the security framework by enabling proactive identification and response to potential security threats.

Future Work: For future improvements, it would be beneficial to consider the following:

- 1) *Refinement of Anomaly Detection Algorithms*: Continuously refine and optimize the anomaly detection algorithms to improve accuracy and reduce false positives. This could involve experimenting with different machine learning models and fine-tuning parameters based on ongoing analysis of security events.
- 2) *Enhancement of Visualization Capabilities*: Explore additional visualization techniques and features in Power BI to provide more comprehensive insights into S3 access patterns. This could include interactive dashboards with drill-down capabilities, geographic mapping of access locations, and trend analysis over time.
- 3) *Integration with Additional AWS Services*: Expand the scope of the project to incorporate data from other AWS services beyond S3 access logs, like Amazon GuardDuty for threat detection. This would provide a more holistic view of cloud security across the entire AWS environment.
- 4) *Streamlining of Workflow Automation*: Streamline the workflow automation process by optimizing Lambda functions and other components for better performance and scalability. This could involve implementing serverless architectures and leveraging AWS Step Functions for orchestration of complex workflows.
- 5) *User Training and Adoption*: Provide training and support to users to ensure proper understanding and utilization of the automated reporting and dashboard tools. This could include developing user guides, conducting training sessions, and soliciting feedback to identify areas for improvement.

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